

THE PLACE OF GRAPHICS IN THE FINE ARTS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the history of the creation of graphics, one of the types of visual arts, the use of a mixture of artistic tools in the form of images in graphic works, graphic techniques and methods.

Keywords: graphics, material, painting, work, line, paper, graphic element, ornament, decorative appearance.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада тасвирий санъат турларидан бири графиканинг яратилиш тарихи, графика асарларида образ кўринишида бадий воситаларнинг аралашмасидан фойдаланиши, графика техникаси ва усулларида ҳақида батафсил маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: графика, материал, рангтасвир, асар, штрих, чизиқ, қоғоз, график элемент, орнамент, декоратив кўриниши.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация об истории создания графики, одного из видов изобразительного искусства, использовании смеси художественных средств в виде изображений в графических произведениях, графических приемах и методах.

Ключевые слова: графика, материал, живопись, произведение, линия, бумага, графический элемент, орнамент, декоративный вид.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek

music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

Among the visual arts, the most common type is graphics. The application possibilities of this art are very wide, the appearance and forms are more diverse. The works of graphic art include book illustrations, labels, easel images and engravings, lithography and theater posters, typefaces for books, etc. Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine our life without these works. Therefore, it is graphics, unlike other types of visual art, that participates in decorating our everyday life around us and has an active influence on people’s lives.

Graphics (Greek - I write, draw, depict) is a type of visual art, which includes:

- 1) drawing (independent and educational field of creativity);
- 2) Various forms of the image (engraving, lithography, etc.).

In graphics, images are created directly: with a pencil, charcoal stick, pencil, silver pen, brush or pen (painting), or specially treated board (engraving), lithography (lithography), mechanical printing process (photomechanical reproduction). The composition can be found in music, theatre, photography, literature, and all kinds of fine arts. [4]

The basis of representation in graphics occupies an important place. Graphic works (or their printed copies) are mostly made on paper, cardboard, in some cases parchment, matte or other (mainly white surface) materials.

The relationship of graphics with other types of visual arts is unique, in motion, changing, like every type of visual arts, the development of graphics in different times was not the same, depending on many factors, it is distinguished by unusual and unrepeatable aspects.

Although graphic images have a centuries-old history, it was not long ago that graphics appeared on the stage of cultural life as a separate type of visual art. The main criteria for development are the figurines of the second type of local sculptors, decorative ornaments and garden sculptures [5]. However, at this time, graphic images began to have their own independent artistic value, and the only signs close to the art of engraving eventually became black-and-white and generally monochrome images executed on a flat surface in the pictorial world (in pencil, charcoal, pen, pastel, and wood), metal, linoleum engravings, etc.) led to the recognition of graphics as a separate type of fine art.

The term “graphics” was originally used to refer to calligraphy and letter writing (in ancient forms of gfařika). In the 19th and 20th centuries, the rapid development of production abroad caused the image to acquire a new meaning.

These images were popularized by O. Berdeli in England, by the artists of “Simplicissimus” magazine in Germany, and by the masters of “Mir iskusstva” magazine in Russia.

Graphic art is defined as black-and-white or line art. This understanding of graphics later led to a great expansion and generalization of new forms of art and new means of representation. In addition to the linear image, the images made with the help of a line and a spot also belong to graphics. Images executed in streaks, spots and mixed media are sharpened (contrast) by the white (rarely color or black) on the surface of the paper, but the harmony of these media creates tonal relationships. Graphics do not deny the use of color. This is achieved through the mental and spiritual development of the students.[6]

In graphic works, the appearance of the image is manifested in the form of an appeal to the viewer's worldview through graphic figurative images, making use of a mixture of more artistic means, and thus graphics is equated with sharia. In graphic techniques and methods, texture has a special place with its own characteristics, it has advantages over painting in terms of the character of the materials used. In graphic works, a stroke, line, spot appears on the paper surface as a graphic element or ornament, decorative and acquires a unique expression.

Graphic art, with its wide range of types, genres, and artistic tools, shows the possibility of a wide image and expresses the artist's feelings and thoughts. Graphic works communicate with the viewer through various methods and means, from a poster with a mass effect to interior photography, paintings, illustrations, and works as miniatures intended for close observation. At the same time, graphics are widely used in the fields of mass communication (mass propaganda, graphic design, advertising and mass media). The unique tariff and application of graphics is that the images are clearly, simply, clearly, and sharply depicted in it. That is why satire and grotesque (caricature, cartoon, multiplicative painting, children's illustrations) became the favorite areas of graphics (Goya's etchings, Daumier's lithographic works, Gross's paintings). An important aspect of graphics is the ability to quickly print, illuminate, and convey current events to the masses.[7]

The British call graphic art “black and white art”. It is different from many other forms of expression, it is distinguished by its bright graphic expression signs, serious features. Black and white graphic art is generally understood as the art of simple black and white harmony with its laconicism. The famous Russian artist V. Favorsky showed the true limits of graphics and said, “there is only

black and white, lines of different thicknesses, spots of different shapes, transition from one form to another, contrasts...”.

Another characteristic of black-and-white graphics is the “conventional” or “attractive” language. But “conventional” graphics, even black-and-white images, illuminate the true images of existence. Studying the laws of black-and-white graphics equips us with a serious artistic weapon and raises our creative activity to a new level.

To sum up, graphic art is the oldest and at the same time constantly updated type of visual art, and today it is shown in more modern forms and is honored.

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